

THE COMPARATIVE STUDY OF COLOUR IDIOMS IN ENGLISH AND KARAKALPAK LANGUAGES

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Abstract. This article explores the comparison of colour idioms in English and Karakalpak, emphasizing on how different languages and cultures conceptualize and express abstract concepts through colour symbolism. Colour idioms play a significant role in language, reflecting cultural values, perceptions, and societal norms. By analyzing a selection of English and Karakalpak colour idioms, this article highlights both similarities and differences in the metaphorical use of colour across languages. Through a comparative analysis, it examines how colours are employed to convey emotions, character traits, and abstract ideas in English and Karakalpak. Furthermore, the article explores the cultural and linguistic factors that shape the meanings and interpretations of colour idioms in each language. Ultimately, this comparative analysis offers insights into the rich tapestry of linguistic diversity and cultural expression embedded within colour idioms, underscoring the importance of language in shaping cultural identity and communication across diverse linguistic communities.

Keywords: colour idioms, comparative analysis, English language, Karakalpak language, cultural symbolism, linguistic diversity

Colour idioms are ubiquitous in language and serve as a window into cultural perceptions, values, and expressions. By examining how different languages utilize colour to convey abstract concepts, we gain insight into the unique linguistic and cultural landscapes of diverse societies. This article explores the comparison of colour idioms in English and Karakalpak, two languages with distinct cultural backgrounds and linguistic traditions [5].

Colour plays a significant role in both English and Karakalpak cultures, serving as a powerful metaphorical tool to describe emotions, character traits, and societal phenomena. However, the specific idiomatic expressions and associations attached to colours may vary between languages, reflecting the cultural nuances and historical contexts that shape language use.

Through a comparative analysis of selected English and Karakalpak colour idioms, this study aims to elucidate both the shared patterns and the unique characteristics of colour symbolism in each language. By examining how colours are employed metaphorically in idiomatic expressions, we can gain a deeper

understanding of the cultural values, beliefs, and worldviews embedded within language.

Also, this study seeks to illuminate the rich tapestry of linguistic diversity and cultural expression encapsulated within colour idioms, highlighting the dynamic interplay between language, culture, and cognition in shaping human communication and perception. Through the exploration of English and Karakalpak colour idioms, we embark on a journey of cross-cultural discovery, uncovering the multifaceted ways in which language reflects and shapes our shared human experience [1].

There are some examples related to English and Karakalpak colour idioms:

1. English:

- "Out of the blue" - Refers to something unexpected or sudden.
- "Green with envy" - Describes someone who is extremely jealous.
- "Black sheep" - Refers to a person who is the odd one out in a group, often with negative connotations.
- "In the red" - Describes a situation where someone is financially struggling or in debt.
- "White lie" - A harmless or trivial lie told to avoid hurting someone's feelings.

2. Karakalpak :

- "Ju'zi qara bolıw" - Refers to a person who feels oneself guilty, doing something shameful.
- "Aq kewil" - Describes someone who is frank, honest, trustworthy.
- "Aq perdesi shig'iw" - Refers to a person who has run out of money, being poor.
- "Qara aspandı tu'siriw" – to exaggerate something
- "Qara suwg'a batiw" – someone who is sweated [7].

These examples illustrate how both English and Karakalpak utilize colour idioms to convey abstract concepts such as emotions, character traits, and situations. While some idioms may have direct equivalents in both languages, others may reflect unique cultural perspectives and associations attached to colours within each linguistic community.

Comparing English and Karakalpak colour idioms can reveal cultural nuances, linguistic diversity, and the ways in which different societies perceive and express emotions, concepts, and experiences through language. It offers insights into how colours are symbolically interpreted and used in each culture, reflecting historical, social, and environmental influences. Additionally, such comparisons can facilitate cross-cultural understanding and appreciation,

fostering communication and empathy across linguistic and cultural boundaries [9].

In conclusion, the comparison of English and Karakalpak colour idioms reveals both similarities and differences in how language and culture shape the metaphorical use of colour. While both languages utilize colour to convey abstract concepts such as emotions, character traits, and societal phenomena, the specific idiomatic expressions and associations attached to each colour may vary significantly between English and Karakalpak. Through this comparative analysis, we have gained insights into the cultural values, beliefs, and worldviews embedded within language, as reflected in the metaphorical use of colour idioms. The study highlights the dynamic interplay between language, culture, and cognition in shaping human communication and perception, underscoring the richness of linguistic diversity and cultural expression across different societies.

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